

Cyclic Voltammetric and Electronic Spectral Studies on the Interaction of Simple and Mixed Ligand Complexes containing Planar NiS₄ and NiS₂P₂ Chromophores with Pyridine

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Transition metal dithiocarbamates are known to react with Lewis bases leading to the formation of the corresponding base adducts¹. However, bis(dialkyldithiocarbamato)nickel(II), Ni(dtc)₂ complexes show interesting variations in their interactions with the Lewis bases². Adduct-forming ability of the dithiocarbamate complexes has been related to the electron-withdrawing ability of the substituent³ and hence to the electron density on the nickel ion⁴. Mostly the axial addition of a Lewis base to planar NiS₄ chromophores has been investigated so far. In continuation of our interest on the structure and reactivities of these type of complexes, adduct-formation of NiS₂PCl and NiS₂P₂ chromophores with pyridine in solution has been investigated by uv-visible spectrometry. The results are related to the reduction potentials of the complexes obtained by cyclic voltammetry.

Results and Discussion

Interaction of the complexes with pyridine: Ni(dedtc)₂ showed absorption bands at 633, 472, 427, 388 and 377 nm in CHCl₃ as reported earlier⁵. The spectrum was not different in pyridine also, which showed that it did not form adduct with pyridine. Similarly, Ni(meadtC)₂ also did not indicate adduct-formation. However, the spectrum of Ni(deadtC)₂ in pyridine showed a split *d-d* absorption band observed due to a distorted octahedral coordination around Ni^{II}. The reactivity of Ni(deadtC)₂ with pyridine, unlike the other two, is due to the presence of two electron-withdrawing C₂H₄OH groups on the dithiocarbamate moiety.

All the three complexes, namely, Ni(dtc)ClPPh₃, dtc = dedtc, meadtC, deadtC decomposed to the respective Ni(dtc)₂ complex on addition of pyridine and hence spectrum could not be recorded for these complexes.

Electronic spectrum of [Ni(dedtc)(PPh₃)₂]ClO₄ in CHCl₃ showed a sharp peak at 490 nm and a shoulder at 615 nm. In pyridine the λ_{max} at 615 nm shifted to a higher value of 627 nm, and 490 nm to a lower value of 465 nm. Similar shifts of the *d-d* band to higher value and the *d-π** charge transfer to lower value were observed for octahedral pyridine adduct with Ni(dedtc)₂ earlier at lower temperature. Therefore, the complex adds pyridine to itself showing characteristics of octahedral geometry. A similar trend was observed in the case of [Ni(meadtC)(PPh₃)₂]⁺ and [Ni(deadtC)(PPh₃)₂]⁺ indicating a positive adduct-forming

interaction with pyridine. The deconvoluted spectrum of [Ni(deadtC)(dppe)]ClO₄ showed *d-d* band around 580 nm which shifted to 620 nm and was asymmetric. The *d-π** charge transfer at 480 nm shifted to 465 nm. Other absorptions were only slightly affected. Similarly, [Ni(deadtC)(dppe)]ClO₄ showed a broad band with maxima at 600 and 620 nm. The shift in λ_{max} with asymmetry in the *d-d* bands is attributed to octahedral geometry. However, the bluish green solution did not yield the solid adduct on evaporation.

Pronounced adduct-forming tendencies associated with NiS₂P₂ chromophore in [Ni(dtc)(PPh₃)₂]⁺ and [Ni(dtc)(dppe)]⁺ over Ni(dtc)₂ is due to lesser electron density on Ni^{II} centre in the former. The presence of phosphorous atom enables the Ni^{II} ion to drain its electron density on to the *d*-orbital of phosphorous. The reduction potentials of the complexes show the following order: Ni(dedtc)Cl(PPh₃) > Ni(dedtc)₂ > [Ni(dedtc)(PPh₃)₂]⁺. The reduction potentials (Table 1) for these complexes along with uv-absorption bands clearly show a correlation between the electron density and adduct-forming ability. [Ni(dtc)(dppe)]⁺ has reduction potential value inbetween Ni(dtc)(PPh₃)Cl and [Ni(dtc)(PPh₃)₂]⁺ which is as expected because of the reduced number of phenyl groups on phosphorous atom⁷.

TABLE I—ABSORPTION BANDS AND REDUCTION POTENTIALS

Compd	λ_{max} * nm	Adduct formation	Reduction potentials**
Ni(dedtc) ₂	633, 472, 427	No	-1.40
Ni(meadtC) ₂	630, 470	No	-1.29
Ni(deadtC) ₂	Band at 630 splits and asymmetric	Yes	-1.38
[Ni(dedtc)Cl(PPh ₃)]	Decomposes in pyridine	—	-1.51
[Ni(dedtc)(PPh ₃) ₂] ⁺	627 band splits, 490 shifts to 465	Yes	-0.80
[Ni(dedtc)(dppe)] ⁺	620 band is asymmetric, 480 band shifts to 460	Yes	-0.88

*In pyridine. **One electron reduction potentials are relative to Ag/AgCl 0.1 mol dm⁻³ LiCl TBAI was used as supporting electrolyte. CH₂Cl₂ was used as solvent.

Of the four types of complexes studied, NiS_2P_2 chromophore showed a higher adduct-forming ability over NiS_4 chromophore. This is attributed to the lesser electron density on Ni^{II} in NiS_2P_2 chromophore. This is further supported by the fact that the cyclic voltammetric experiments on these complexes showed a minimum reduction potential with respect to NiS_2P_2 chromophore. The less negative reduction potential is due to extensive π -back-bonding between nickel and the two phosphorous atoms.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes : $\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})_2$ complexes were prepared by mixing the corresponding freshly prepared dithiocarbamic acid, NiCl_2 and various amines such as monoethanolamine, diethanolamine and diethylamine. The corresponding dithiocarbamates, $\text{Ni}(\text{meadtc})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{deadtc})_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{dedtc})_2$ were refluxed in ethanol with one equivalent of PPh_3 and NiCl_2 for 30 min. Solid purple coloured complexes obtained were analysed to the general formula $\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})\text{ClPPh}_3^5$. However, $\text{Ni}(\text{meadtc})\text{ClPPh}_3$ was highly unstable and could not be separated. The purple coloured solids were suspended in methanol and one equivalent of PPh_3 and LiClO_4 were added and refluxed for 30 min. The dark red crystalline complexes obtained were analysed to the general formula $[\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4$.

Similarly, chelating phosphine, $\text{dppe} = 1,2$ -bis(diphenylphosphino)ethane was added to $\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})\text{ClPPh}_3$ along with LiClO_4 in methanol to separate $[\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})(\text{dppe})]\text{ClO}_4$ complexes. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic and hence are planar Ni^{II} complexes. Electronic spectra of these complexes were recorded on a JASCO UVIDEDEC-90 spectrophotometer. Cyclic voltammetric study was made with PAR-electrochemical systems. Pt-wire was used as a working electrode with Ag-AgCl in $\text{LiCl}/\text{acetone}$ as the reference electrode. Dichloromethane was used as the solvent.

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